

Boiled & Pounded Yam, Gari-Eba Food Target Product Profiles Workplan, at IITA-Nigeria

Kampala, Uganda, October 2025

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This report has been written in the framework of the RTBfoodomics project (under CIRAD coordination), as a continuation of work initiated under the RTBfoods and RTB Breeding projects.

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Ethics: The activities, which led to the production of this document, were assessed and approved by the CIRAD Ethics Committee (H2020 ethics self-assessment procedure). When relevant, samples were prepared according to good hygiene and manufacturing practices. When external participants were involved in an activity, they were priorly informed about the objective of the activity and explained that their participation was entirely voluntary, that they could stop the interview at any point and that their responses would be anonymous and securely stored by the research team for research purposes.

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Background

Roots, tubers, and bananas (RTB) are vital to food security, income generation, and climate resilience for millions of smallholder farming households across sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). These crops—cassava, yam, sweetpotato, banana, and plantain—are staple foods that not only provide calories but also serve as key sources of income during seasonal food shortages. While past breeding efforts have successfully improved productivity and disease resistance, adoption of new varieties has often lagged due to poor alignment with consumer preferences for food quality traits such as texture, flavor, aroma, and ease of processing.

The RTBfoods project (2017–2022), made significant progress in identifying and characterizing user-preferred food quality traits across diverse geographies. It established robust sensory evaluation methods, generated consumer acceptance data, and developed Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) for food phenotyping. However, a critical knowledge gap remains: the biochemical basis of these traits and how they can be measured and selected for in breeding pipelines for breakthrough varieties.

The **RTBfoodomics project** builds on this foundation by integrating **metabolomics** into RTB breeding programs. Metabolomics enables the identification of chemical compounds and pathways that underlie sensory qualities, offering an objective, high-resolution approach to link genotype to phenotype. By capturing and characterizing the metabolite profiles—or *chemotypes*—of RTB crops associated with preferred and non-preferred traits, the project will enable the development of metabolite-based proxy markers. These can be deployed in high-throughput screening tools, supporting breeders to more efficiently select for consumer-relevant traits.

This approach is expected to accelerate genetic gains, improve the relevance of new RTB breakthrough varieties, and increase adoption by smallholder farmers, processors, and consumers. Through strong partnerships with national and international research institutions, the project will generate public-good data, strengthen capacity for food trait phenotyping and metabolomics, and provide actionable insights to guide breeding decisions.

RTBfoodomics aligns with the Gates Foundation’s broader strategy to modernize breeding and increase productivity and income for small-scale producers by delivering breakthrough varieties that not only perform agronomically but also meet market and consumer demand.

RTBfoodomics Project Snapshot	
Project Title	RTBfoodomics: RTB Food Quality – Refining Targets with Metabolomics
Lead Organization	CIRAD (French Agricultural Research Centre for International Development)
Key Partners	IITA, CIAT, CIP, NaCCRI, NRCRI, NARO, RHUL, National & Regional Breeding Programs
Funding Agency	Gates Foundation
Project Duration	November 2024 – October 2027
Total Budget	USD 1.9 million (Requested grant: USD 1.5 million)
Geographic Focus	Sub-Saharan Africa (multi-country implementation across major RTB regions)
Primary Goal	To identify and integrate consumer-preferred food quality traits (e.g., aroma, texture, flavor) into RTB breeding programs using metabolomic tools
Core Activities	Metabolomic profiling, sensory evaluation, development of proxy assays, quality trait mapping, and integration of findings into breeding pipelines
Target Crops & Products	Cassava (eba, gari), Yam (boiled, pounded), Plantain (boiled, fried), Banana (matooke), Sweetpotato (boiled)
Expected Outcomes	Chemotype databases, quality-linked biomarkers, high-throughput screening protocols, and greater adoption of improved RTB varieties by end users

The IITA's Role in the RTBFoodomics Project

The International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA) plays a central role in implementing the RTBfoodomics project through two main components (Figure 1):

- a) Breeding Program - supplying genetically diverse breeding materials. The sampling strategies involved at least 15 (good, intermediate, poor) genotypes; and 6 biological replicates.
- b) Food and Nutrition Sciences Laboratory - conducting comprehensive food quality evaluations, sample preparation and shipping.

Breeding Program: IITA's yam, cassava, and banana/plantain breeding programs are contributing genotypes selected to represent a range of food quality traits—good, intermediate, and poor.

- **Yam:** 36 diverse yam genotypes—20 *Dioscorea rotundata* and 16 *Dioscorea alata*—were selected based on both historical and recent sensory analysis data (see Appendix 1 for the full list).
- **Cassava:** 48 genotypes, selected from the genetically diverse PYT 52 trial, were chosen based on key agronomic and product quality traits, including yield, dry matter content, carotenoid levels, and eba texture (see Appendix 2 for the full list).
- **Plantain:** 8 genotypes were selected based on breeder expertise and market acceptance, encompassing widely preferred landraces, improved varieties, and lines previously rejected due to poor postharvest performance (see Appendix 3 for the full list).

Lab: Complementing the breeding program, IITA's Food and Nutrition Sciences Laboratory is responsible for the biochemical and sensory characterization of the selected genotypes using validated RTBfoods protocols. Key tasks include Quantitative Descriptive Analysis (QDA) with trained sensory panels, instrumental texture assessments, and sample preparation. Fresh (**cassava, yam, and plantain**) and processed products (**boiled and pounded yam, gari and eba from cassava, and boiled and fried plantain**) will be freeze-dried and shipped to Royal Holloway University of London (RHUL) for metabolomic profiling, and some frozen samples will be sent to CIRAD (French Agricultural Research Centre for International Development) for aroma analysis.

Through this dual role, the contributions of IITA ensure that the RTBfoodomics project is grounded in both genetic and food quality evidence, enabling the integration of end-user traits into breeding pipelines.

Figure 1: Workflow plan from crop fields to the laboratories

Implementation Plan by Crop

Cassava

Sampling and Sample Preparation Strategy

The cassava sampling strategy for RTBfoodomics involves the evaluation of 48 genotypes—comprising 45 advanced breeding lines and 3 landraces—planted in two replications and assessed for key quality traits, including instrumental texture and biochemical composition. These genotypes are established across three locations using a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with two replications. Each plot measures 5.6 m × 6 m, with 1 m spacing between rows and 0.8 m within rows. Roots will be harvested 12 months after planting, and six biological replicates per genotype will be processed into gari. The resulting gari samples will be transferred to the laboratory for quality characterization, including biochemical, instrumental, and sensory texture analyses. Based on initial results, 15 diverse genotypes—classified as good (n=5), intermediate (n=5), and poor (n=5)—will be purposively selected. These selected samples will be freeze-dried and shipped via DHL to RHUL for metabolomic profiling. Samples designated for aroma analysis will be couriered to CIRAD. All quality evaluations will follow the validated RTBfoods Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) outlined in Appendix 4.

Figure 2: Schematic sampling and sample preparation workflow for fresh cassava and Gari/Eba

Cassava Food Trait Product Profile (FTPP) Quality Characterisation

The IITA team has identified key quality traits (KQTs) for gari and eba, informed by historical data and findings from the RTBfoods project. The prioritized traits include texture, swelling index, and color. Among the textural attributes, hardness and cohesiveness have been found to correlate strongly with consumer preferences. A comprehensive list of Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) for assessing these traits is provided in Appendix 4.

Color parameters (L^* , a^* , b^*) will be measured using a chromameter, following the established SOP. Both Instrumental Texture Profile Analysis (ITPA) and Quantitative Descriptive Analysis (QDA) will be conducted according to validated SoPs. Table 1 summarizes the key quality parameters aligned with each product profile.

Table 1: Quality traits assessed for Fresh Cassava and Gari/Eba

Fresh Cassava	Gari	Eba (Texture/Sensory)
Dry matter	Pasting	Hardness
Color	Swelling index	Cohesiveness
	Color	Mouldability
	Water Absorption Capacity	
	Solubility	

Implementation Timeline:

Table 2: 2025-2026 RTBFoodomics IITA project implementation timeline for cassava

Activity	Activity details	Sub-activity	2025		2026						
			May	June	July	August	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	
Planting	Planting and plot management meta-data: 48 genotypes, 3 locations, 6 replicates	10 stands/plot	X								
Harvest	Roots harvesting	Labeling, coding, and document sample transfer		X							
Analysis	Fresh sample processing	Freeze-drying		X							
		Dry matter, starch, color (Lab), etc.		X							
	Product processing: gari	Soaking, grating, and fermentation (3 days)		X							
	Lab analysis: gari	Biophysical – Color, Rheology, swelling index, solubility, particle size, etc.			X						
	Lab analysis: eba	Texture – TPA, color, etc.			X	X					
	Sensory panel scoring (QDA)	Color, texture, taste, aroma			X	X					
	Consumer scoring	Overall liking, color, texture.				X	X				
Sample transfer	Sample to RHUL	Metabolomics				X	X				
	Sample to CIRAD	Aroma profiling				X	X				
Reporting	Data analysis						X	X	X	X	
	Reporting										
	Publication										

Yam

Sampling and Sample Preparation Strategy

A total of 36 yam genotypes, comprising 20 *Dioscorea rotundata* (white Guinea yam) and 16 *Dioscorea alata* (water yam), were selected based on historical and recent data related to texture and overall food quality. Selection criteria included culinary evaluations of both boiled and pounded yam, supported by sensory panel assessments. Hierarchical clustering analysis was used to classify the genotypes into three food quality categories: good, intermediate, and poor. The *D. rotundata* genotypes will be planted at two locations, while *D. alata* genotypes will be planted at three locations, depending on tuber availability. Proposed field trial sites include Ibadan, Ikenne, and Abuja. Trials will follow a row-column design: a 5 × 4 layout for *D. rotundata* and a 4 × 4 layout for *D. alata*, with two replications per location and 10 plants per genotype per replication.

Data on quality traits will be collected at harvest and throughout storage to capture time-dependent changes. Sensory evaluation will complement metabolomic profiling and will be conducted on both boiled and pounded yam products for each species. Sensory attributes will be assessed on both raw and cooked samples, including homogenized, freeze-dried tissues designated for metabolomic analysis at RHUL. For boiled yam, freeze dried samples will be sent to CIRAD for aroma analysis.

Figure 3: Schematic sampling and sample preparation workflow for fresh yam, boiled, and pounded yam

Yam Food Trait Product Profile (FTPP) Quality Characterisation

The IITA team has identified key quality traits (KQTs) for each yam product profile, drawing on historical data and insights from the RTBfoods project. For boiled yam, the prioritized traits include texture—specifically hardness and chewiness—along with color and aroma. For pounded yam, the key attributes influencing consumer preference are stretchability and mouldability.

Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) for evaluating these traits are provided in Appendix 5. Color parameters (L^* , a^* , b^*) will be measured on both fresh and boiled yam using a chromameter, in accordance with the prescribed SOPs. Instrumental Texture Profile Analysis (ITPA) and Quantitative Descriptive Analysis (QDA) will be conducted for both boiled and pounded yam, following the prescribed SOPs. Table 3 summarizes the key quality parameters for each yam product profile.

Table 3: Quality traits for fresh, boiled and pounded yam

Fresh yam	Boiled yam	Pounded yam
Dry matter	Color	Hardness
Color	Penetrometry	Cohesiveness
	Taste	Stretchability
	Aroma	

Implementation Timeline

Table 4: 2025-2026 RTBFoodomics IITA project implementation timeline for yam

Activity	Activity details	Sub-activity	2025			2026		
			April	Nov	Dec	Jan - Jun	Feb	Jun - Sep
Planting	Planting and plot management meta-data: 36 genotypes, 2-3 locations, 6 replicates	20 <i>Dioscorea rotundata</i> (white Guinea yam) 16 <i>Dioscorea alata</i> (water yam)	X					
Harvest	Roots harvesting	Labeling, coding, and document sample transfer		X				
Analysis	Fresh sample processing	Freeze- drying			X			
		Dry matter, starch, texture, color (Lab), etc.			X			
	Processed yam sample	Boiled yam – penetrometry.			X			
		Pounded yam - extensibility			X			
	Sensory panel scoring (QDA) - fresh	Color, texture, taste, aroma			X			
Storage study	Texture, QDA, biochemical				X			
Sample transfer	Sample to RHUL	Metabolomics					X	
	Sample to CIRAD	Aroma profiling					X	
Reporting	Data analysis	Data management						X
	Reporting							
	Publication							

Budget: 2025-2026 – Analysis plan

IITA RTBfoodomics Budget for 2025-2026 Analysis				
Budget details		Genotype	No. of biological replication	No. of samples
Cassava		52.00	2.00	104.00
Product Profile	Traits	Unit Cost (\$)	No of sample	Amount (\$)
Fresh Cassava	Dry Matter	7.50	104.00	780.00
	Color	2.50	104.00	260.00
	Freeze-drying (15 selected genotypes x 6 biological rep)	100.00	90.00	9,000.00
Gari	Color	2.50	104.00	260.00
	Pasting properties	10.50	104.00	1,092.00
	Swelling Index	4.50	104.00	468.00
	Swelling power & Solubility	5.25	104.00	546.00
Eba	Color	2.50	104.00	260.00
	Sensory	20.00	52.00	1,040.00
	Texture (ITPA)	10.00	52.00	520.00
	Freeze-drying (15 selected genotypes x 6 biological rep)	100.00	90.00	9,000.00
Shipment		800.00	1.00	800.00
subtotal				24,026.00
Yam		36.00	3.00	108.00
Product Profile	Traits	Unit Cost (\$)	No of sample	Amount (\$)
Fresh yam	Dry Matter	7.50	108.00	810.00
	Color	2.50	108.00	270.00
	Freeze-drying	100.00	108.00	10,800.00
Boiled yam	Sensory	20.00	72.00	1,440.00
	Color	2.50	72.00	180.00
	Texture (Penetrometry)	10.00	72.00	720.00
	Freeze-drying	100.00	90.00	9,000.00
Pounded yam	Sensory	20.00	72.00	1,440.00
	Texture (Extensibility)	10.00	72.00	720.00
	Freeze-drying	100.00	90.00	9,000.00
Shipment		800.00	1.00	800.00
subtotal				35,180.00
Plantain		80.00		80.00
Product Profile	Traits	Unit Cost (\$)	No of sample	Amount (\$)
Fresh plantain	Dry Matter	7.50	80.00	600.00
	Color	2.50	80.00	200.00
	Freeze-drying	100.00	80.00	8,000.00
Fried plantain	Sensory	20.00	80.00	1,600.00
	Color	2.50	80.00	200.00
	Texture (Hardness)	10.00	80.00	800.00
	Freeze-drying	100.00	90.00	9,000.00
Shipment		800.00	1.00	800.00
subtotal				21,200.00
Personnel Cost :1	1 Research Assistant	8,000.00	1.00	8,000.00
Sensory Testing	Compusense software	5,500.00	3.00	16,500.00
subtotal				24,500.00
Total				104,906.00

Appendices

Appendix 1

Selected white yam and water yam to be used for the FoodOmics study.

SN	Genotypes	Breeding status	Species	Location
1	TDr1716010	Breeding line	<i>D. rotundata</i>	Ibn & Abj
2	TDr1716041	Breeding line	<i>D. rotundata</i>	Ibn & Abj
3	TDr1719059	Breeding line	<i>D. rotundata</i>	Ibn & Abj
4	TDr1719065	Breeding line	<i>D. rotundata</i>	Ibn & Abj
5	TDr1739060	Breeding line	<i>D. rotundata</i>	Ibn & Abj
6	TDr1739063	Breeding line	<i>D. rotundata</i>	Ibn & Abj
7	TDr1739084	Breeding line	<i>D. rotundata</i>	Ibn & Abj
8	TDr1741024	Breeding line	<i>D. rotundata</i>	Ibn & Abj
9	TDr1741074	Breeding line	<i>D. rotundata</i>	Ibn & Abj
10	TDr1437005	Breeding line	<i>D. rotundata</i>	Ibn & Abj
11	TDr1401220	Breeding line	<i>D. rotundata</i>	Ibn & Abj
12	Boss	Farmer variety	<i>D. rotundata</i>	Ibn & Abj
13	Aloshi	Farmer variety	<i>D. rotundata</i>	Ibn & Abj
14	TDr19144010	Breeding line	<i>D. rotundata</i>	Ibn & Abj
14	TDr9519177	Breeding line	<i>D. rotundata</i>	Ibn & Abj
16	TDr1439027	Breeding line	<i>D. rotundata</i>	Ibn & Abj
17	TDr1400158	Breeding line	<i>D. rotundata</i>	Ibn & Abj
18	TDr150042	Breeding line	<i>D. rotundata</i>	Ibn & Abj
19	TDr1669010	Breeding line	<i>D. rotundata</i>	Ibn & Abj
20	TDr8902665	Breeding line	<i>D. rotundata</i>	Ibn & Abj
21	TDa0000194	Breeding line	<i>D. alata</i>	Ibn, Ikn & Benin
22	Oweigbo	Farmer variety	<i>D. alata</i>	Ibn, Ikn & Benin
23	TDa1741010	Breeding line	<i>D. alata</i>	Ibn, Ikn & Benin
24	TDa174002	Breeding line	<i>D. alata</i>	Ibn, Ikn & Benin
25	TDa1724001	Breeding line	<i>D. alata</i>	Ibn, Ikn & Benin
26	TDa1741004	Breeding line	<i>D. alata</i>	Ibn, Ikn & Benin
27	TDa1729002	Breeding line	<i>D. alata</i>	Ibn, Ikn & Benin
28	TDa1738001	Breeding line	<i>D. alata</i>	Ibn, Ikn & Benin
29	TDa1100316	Breeding line	<i>D. alata</i>	Ibn, Ikn & Benin
30	Akwubata	Breeding line	<i>D. alata</i>	Ibn, Ikn & Benin
31	TDa1723003	Breeding line	<i>D. alata</i>	Ibn, Ikn & Benin
32	TDa1741006	Breeding line	<i>D. alata</i>	Ibn, Ikn & Benin
33	TDa1741007	Breeding line	<i>D. alata</i>	Ibn, Ikn & Benin
34	TDa1520050	Breeding line	<i>D. alata</i>	Ibn, Ikn & Benin
35	TDa1510119	Breeding line	<i>D. alata</i>	Ibn, Ikn & Benin
36	TDa1662006	Breeding line	<i>D. alata</i>	Ibn, Ikn & Benin

Notes: Ibn: Ibadan; Ikn: Ikenne; Abj: Abuja.

Appendix 2

Selected cassava genotypes to be used for Foodomics study

SN	Genotypes	Breeding status	Location
1	IITA-TMS-IBA000070	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
2	IITA-TMS-IBA011231	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
3	IITA-TMS-IBA011368	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
4	IITA-TMS-IBA011412	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
5	IITA-TMS-IBA011663	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
6	IITA-TMS-IBA020510	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
7	IITA-TMS-IBA030006A	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
8	IITA-TMS-IBA050128	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
9	IITA-TMS-IBA051599	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
10	IITA-TMS-IBA051601	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
11	IITA-TMS-IBA051652	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
12	IITA-TMS-IBA051814	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
13	IITA-TMS-IBA061101	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
14	IITA-TMS-IBA061635	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
15	IITA-TMS-IBA070064	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
16	IITA-TMS-IBA070536	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
17	IITA-TMS-IBA070808	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
18	IITA-TMS-IBA070910	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
19	IITA-TMS-IBA071313	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
20	IITA-TMS-IBA071378	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
21	IITA-TMS-IBA082993	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
22	IITA-TMS-IBA083580	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
23	IITA-TMS-IBA083724	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
24	IITA-TMS-IBA090091	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
25	IITA-TMS-IBA090144	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
26	IITA-TMS-IBA090454	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
27	IITA-TMS-IBA090485	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
28	IITA-TMS-IBA090576	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
29	IITA-TMS-IBA102103	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
30	IITA-TMS-IBA30572	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
31	IITA-TMS-IBA950925	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
32	IITA-TMS-IBA980581	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
33	IITA-TMS-IBA982101	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
34	IITA-TMS-IBA990304	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
35	IITA-TMS-MM972346	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
36	IITA-TMS-MM990214	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
37	IITA-TMS-MM990302	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
38	IITA-TMS-ZAR010116	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
39	KALESO	Farmer variety	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
40	SIMONYE	Farmer variety	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
41	TMEB419	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
42	TMEB693	Farmer variety	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
43	TMS13F1053P0010	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
44	TMS13F1053P0015	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
45	TMS13F1088P0007	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
46	TMS13F1153P0001	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
47	TMS13F1343P0002	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj
48	TMS13F1343P0022	Breeding line	Ibn, Ikn & Ubj

Notes: Ibn: Ibadan; Ikn: Ikenne, Ubj: Ubiaja.

Appendix 3

Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) for Cassava Quality Evaluation

SN	Standard Operating Procedures (SOP)	doi
1	SOP for sensory characterization of Eba.	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00596
2	Training a panel in sensory analysis and implementing descriptive tests. How to process data.	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00573
3	Monitoring panel performance and cleaning data from descriptive sensory panels for statistical analysis	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00582
4	Statistics (PCA and multiple regression) to Visualise Sensory Analysis & Relate it to the Instrumental Data	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00710
5	SOP for textural characterization of Eba.	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00604

Appendix 4

Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) for Yam Quality Evaluation

SN	Standard Operating Procedures (SOP)	doi
1	SOP for sensory characterization of boiled yam.	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00600
2	Training a panel in sensory analysis and implementing descriptive tests. How to process data.	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00573
3	Monitoring panel performance and cleaning data from descriptive sensory panels for statistical analysis	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00582
4	Statistics (PCA and multiple regression) to Visualise Sensory Analysis & Relate it to the Instrumental Data	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00710
5	SOP for Sample Preparation and the Measurement of Texture of Boiled Yam	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00786
6	SOP for Determination of Extensibility of Pounded Yam using Kieffer Dough Extensibility Method	https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00787
7	SOP for Sample Preparation and Operation of Labconco Freeze Dryer	In-house

Appendix 5

IITA RTBfoodomics Project Team

Team member	Role
Mercy Lungaho	RTBFoodomics Focal point/ Plantain, Research support
Michael Adesokan	Gari/Eba - Research support
Segun Fawole	Boiled yam - Research support
Bolanle Otegbayo	Pounded yam - Research support
Ismail Rabbi	Cassava crop lead – Crop support
Asrat Amele	Yam crop lead – Crop support
Moses Nyine	Plantain crop lead – Crop support
Richard Ofei	Project execution/Finance
Hapson Mushoriwa	Head of Breeding/Coordination